

**A SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS OF PRACTICAL AND CONCEPTUAL
SPHERE OF MODERN TRANSLATION**

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Annotation: *Translation theory is a logically based model of bilingual communication; it is a theoretical part of translation linguistics (a branch of linguistics that studies translation as a linguistic phenomenon).*

Key words: *Concept of translation, modern linguistics and the impact of information theory, functional, language, learning.*

A systematic analysis of translation practice and the conceptual sphere of modern translation studies allow us to build a single typology of translations that summarizes various aspects of translation preparation, implementation, presentation and functioning and correlates with other main components of translation activities.

Translations are typologized according to the following parameters::

- ❖ correlation between the types of the translation language and the original language;
- ❖ presentation form for the translation and original texts;
- ❖ how the translation text matches the original text;
- ❖ genre-stylistic features and genre affiliation of the translated material;

Translations that are distinguished by the ratio of the types of the target language and the original language:

- a. diachronic (historical) translation – translation of a historical text into a modern language;
- b. transposition – translation of a text from one genre to another genre;
- c. interlanguage translation is the transformation of a message expressed by means of one sign system into a message expressed by means of another sign system.

Translations that are distinguished by the general characteristics of the subject of translation activity and its relation to the author of the translated text:

- ❖ traditional (human, manual) translation – translation performed by a person.
- ❖ machine (automatic) – executed or executed by a computer;
- ❖ mixed – using a significant amount of traditional (or machine) text processing.
- ❖ Translations performed by the type of translation segmentation of the text and by the translation units used:
 - ❖ morpheme translation. – at the level of individual morphemes without taking into account their structural relationships;
 - ❖ word-by-word – separate words without taking into account semantic, syntactic and stylistic connections between words;
 - ❖ phrase-by-phrase – separate sentences or phrases that are translated sequentially one after the other;
 - ❖ paragraph-phrase translation – separate sentences or paragraphs that are translated sequentially one after the other;
 - ❖ full-text – whole text, without highlighting individual words, sentences, or paragraphs as separate translation units.

Translations that are selected based on the nature and quality of the translation text matching the original text:

- ❖ free translation-reproduces the basic information of the original with possible deviations – additions, omissions, etc.; It is carried out at the text level, so the categories of equivalence of language units are irrelevant for it.
- ❖ accurate (correct) translation-characterized by the property of semantic accuracy, i.e. semantically fully and correctly conveys the plan of the original content;
- ❖ authentic translation – a translation of an official document that has the same legal force as the original; according to international law, the text of a treaty can be developed and adopted in one language, but its authenticity is established in two or more languages;
- ❖ Translations that are distinguished by their main pragmatic function:
- ❖ practical translation – intended for practical use as a source of information.
- ❖ training – used in the educational process for training translators or as one of the methods of teaching a foreign language;

Translations that are selected based on the primacy or non-primacy of the original text:

- ❖ direct (primary, direct) – made directly from the original;
- ❖ indirect (secondary, indirect) – made not directly from the original text, but from its translation into some other language;
- ❖ reverse-experimental or educational translation of an already translated text into the source language.

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